

Cluster Head Selection in Wireless Sensor Network using Energy-Efficient Grey Wolf Optimization (MEEGWO)

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Abstract: Researchers in the field of telecommunications have long been interested in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs). Wide-area sensor networks (WSNs) are formed by large numbers of sensor nodes that combine sensing, processing, and wireless communication capabilities. Sensing systems that monitor and control physical and environmental processes frequently use these networks. Nevertheless, the lengthy operating lifespan of WSNs is sometimes limited by the high energy consumption of network nodes, which is a major difficulty in the field. In this study, MATLAB was utilized as a simulation platform to evaluate and contrast the efficiency with which three protocols for wireless sensor networks optimize energy consumption: the Fuzzy Protocol, Energy Efficient Grey Wolf Optimization (MEEGWO), and Modified Low-energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy (MLEACH). The simulations focused on assessing the number of active sensor nodes and evaluating the network's lifespan by measuring the percentage of non-operational (dead) nodes, which are critical metrics for determining protocol effectiveness. Results indicated that MEEGWO outperformed both Fuzzy and MLEACH protocols. Here survivability of MEEGWO is 25% more than Fuzzy and 27% more than MLEACH and number of dead node are more increase as number of rounds are increase in Fuzzy and MLEACH whereas number of dead nodes in less in MEEGWO, it perform more well in 1300 round to 1700 rounds .

KEYWORDS: LEACH clustering, cluster head, grey wolf optimization, optimization, wireless sensor networks, MLEACH etc.

1. Introduction

As commonly understood, a wireless sensor network operates through tiny sensor nodes powered by low-capacity batteries, featuring limited storage, processing capabilities, and radio functionality. These networks are deployed both indoors and outdoors, expected to operate autonomously, continuously monitoring designated areas and transmitting data to a central base station [1].

Given that the precise locations of individual sensor nodes are not predetermined, the network necessary self-configuration capabilities. Protocol designs for such networks must prioritize energy efficiency to extend the network's lifespan, as replacing embedded batteries post-installation is challenging. To ensure effective monitoring, wireless sensor networks must utilize their energy resources wisely. A typical sensor node comprises four key components: a power unit, transceiver unit, processing unit, and sensing element. Power generators, mobility support, and location monitoring systems may be additional application-specific components.

To maintain a WSN effectively, conserving energy is vital. Clustering offers an efficient and straightforward approach to achieve this goal.

Clustering involves organizing multiple nodes within a Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) into groups and facilitating interaction between the cluster and the Base Station (BS) via a designated leader known as the CH. Choosing clusters and the respective CHs presents a formidable and intricate challenge. There are a lot of methods that have been used to find the best CHs over the years [2-3] As shown in Figure 1, WSN clustering.

Figure.1 Network model with clustering

Over time, a diverse range of optimization methodology has been utilized to determine the optimal selection of cluster heads (CHs) within a network [4–8]. These methodologies span various computational and heuristic approaches, such as fuzzy logic, genetic algorithms, artificial bee colony optimization, ant colony optimization, particle swarm optimization, and harmony search algorithms [9]. Each of these techniques leverages unique mechanisms to enhance the efficiency and reliability of cluster head selection, contributing to improved network performance and resource management.

In this paper, we present the Modified Energy Efficient Grey Wolf Optimization (MEEGWO) technique as an innovative solution to address the cluster head (CH) selection problem in wireless networks. This approach is inspired by the natural hunting and leadership hierarchy of

grey wolves in the wild, translating their social dynamics into computational strategies for optimization. In the MEEGWO algorithm, the grey wolves represent potential solutions, with the alpha wolves symbolizing the most optimal solutions based on their fitness, while beta, delta, and omega wolves represent progressively less optimal alternatives. By simulating this hierarchy, the technique ensures a structured exploration and exploitation of the solution space, ultimately leading to the selection of energy-efficient and high-performing cluster heads

The subsequent sections of the paper are ordered as follows: Section 2 presents a thorough review of existing studies in clustering of the sensor nodes. Section 3 delves into the Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) technique, offering an in-depth explanation of its principles, mechanics, and applicability to optimization problems. Section 4 outlines energy model. Section 5 elaborates on the proposed MEEGWO protocol. Section 6 covers the simulation model. Finally, Section 7 presents simulation results along with their discussion and Section 8 conclude the paper

2. Literature Review

This scenario uses the Low-Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy (LEACH), a well-known and traditional clustering methodology, as a starting point. According to LEACH's probabilistic mechanism, a specified threshold is compared to the random numbers generated by each sensor node in the network, which range from 0 to 1. The sensor node takes over as the CH if the produced value is less than the threshold. Then, nodes that aren't CHs link up with the closest CH, and the CH uses a TDMA technique to coordinate when the non-CHs' transmissions will take place.

Despite its simplicity, LEACH exhibits significant limitations, including suboptimal performance and the potential selection of nodes with low energy as CHs, leading to premature node failure. To mitigate these drawbacks, various alternative protocols have been developed. For instance, LEACH-Centralized (LEACH-C) incorporates residual energy into the CH selection process, while protocols such as the Stable Election Protocol (SEP) and Energy-Efficient Heterogeneous Clustering (EEHC) cater specifically to heterogeneous networks. These protocols designate certain nodes as advanced nodes with higher energy reserves to extend network longevity.

Improvements in clustering methods were prompted by the shortcomings of these initial procedures. Among them, the two most notable are Distributed Energy-Efficient Clustering (DEEC) and Power-Efficient Gathering in Sensor Information Systems (PEGASIS) [18]. The Hybrid Distributed Energy-Efficient Heterogeneous Clustering Protocol (HDEEHC) was introduced because, although HEED provides energy-efficient clustering, it has performance issues in heterogeneous contexts. This approach improves CH selection in heterogeneous networks by using characteristics including residual energy, node degree, and node type [19].

Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) continue to face the issue of energy consumption, which has led to the development of more sophisticated protocols. One approach that uses a fixed clustering structure and picks CHs depending on residual energy to prolong the network's lifespan is Energy-Efficient Layered Clustering (EEHC) [20].

Optimization approaches have increasingly been utilized to tackle difficulties in WSN. Among these, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) demonstrates significant potential, offering advantages like improved solution accuracy and computational efficiency. In PSO-based clustering approaches, the node closest to the BS within a cluster is often selected as the CH, reducing energy consumption [21]. By factoring in residual energy and node distance, variants like PSO-C enhance CH selection and achieve better throughput and network durability than LEACH and LEACH-C [22-23]. PSO is also employed for applications like intra-cluster distance reduction, mobile WSN coverage optimization, and energy-efficient node deployment [24-27].

Emerging techniques, such as Social Group Optimization (SGO), focus on minimizing data transmission distance and conserving node energy. Additionally, the Fitness Value-Based Improved Grey Wolf Optimization (FIGWO) protocol applies the Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) framework, employing a fitness function to prioritize CHs with higher energy and proximity to the BS. FIGWO recalculates transmission distance during each CH election but faces challenges in balancing workloads across CHs [30-31].

Other approaches, like Tabu PSO, optimize route selection for improving cluster formation, node survivability, and reducing packet loss and transmission delays [32]. Hierarchical clustering with Type-2 fuzzy logic and the A GAOC protocol is a genetic algorithm-based optimized clustering method which further enhance the network efficiency, particularly in heterogeneous and mobile WSN environments [33-34].

Building upon these advancements, this paper introduces the Modified Energy Efficient Grey Wolf Optimizer (MEEGWO) for CH selection. MEEGWO outperforms traditional metaheuristic techniques due to its faster convergence rate, effective reduction of the search space, and fewer decision variables. By avoiding local optima and ensuring balanced workload distribution among CHs, when compared to competing solutions, MEEGWO's network energy efficiency and lifetime are noticeably better. This paper also provides a comparative analysis of MEEGWO against other clustering methods to highlight its advantages.

3. Grey Wolf Optimization

The social structure and cooperative hunting techniques of grey wolves served as inspiration for the nature-based algorithm known as Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO). Mirjalili et al. [10] first proposed the GWO algorithm in 2014; to solve complicated optimization problems recursively, it mimics the pack hierarchy found in wolves.

In GWO, the search process unfolds in an abstract search space, analogous to grey wolves hunting prey. The wolves represent potential solutions, and the prey signifies the optimal solution sought. The algorithm operates through four key steps:

1. Initialization:

As a representation of the initial solutions to the optimization issue, grey wolves are started off with random positions in the search space.

2. Alpha, Beta, and Delta Positions:

The leadership of the pack directs the search process, and the three best solutions found in each iteration are called alpha, beta, and delta wolves, respectively.

3. Updating Positions:

The placements of the alpha, beta, and delta wolves determine how the remaining wolves, known as omega wolves, are updated. Here, we model the hunting strategies of grey wolves using mathematical equations.

4. Solution Update:

Until the stopping criterion which could be a maximum number of iterations or a tolerable error margin is satisfied, the alpha wolf's position representing the best solution is modified iteratively.

GWO's strength lies in its ability to quickly converge to near-optimal solutions, especially in optimization problems with continuous search spaces.

When hunting, grey wolves will encircle and encircle their prey. The following is a scientific expression of this encircling behavior

$$\Delta Xi = K \cdot Xp - Xi \cdot r1 - Xj \cdot r2 \tag{1}$$

$$Xi(t+1) = Xp - A \cdot D \tag{2}$$

In these equations:

The *i*th gray wolf's displacement is shown by the vector ΔXi , while Xi indicates the wolf's location and Xp represents the prey's location. A constant coefficient is denoted by K . Vectors $r1$ and $r2$ are completely at random. "A" stands for a coefficient. The geometric distance (D) between points Xp and Xi is represented. t is the number of iterations

The vector equation can be computed as follows

$$\Delta Xi = 2 \cdot a \cdot r1 - a \cdot Xi \tag{3}$$

Where, ΔXi represents the displacement vector of the *i*th grey wolf, a is a constant coefficient. $r1i$ is a random vector, Xi represents the position of the *i*th grey wolf.

4. Energy dissipation model

The energy level of a node fluctuates as it transmits and receives signals. Several factors contribute to the energy expenditure during transmission (E_{tx}), including: (i) the energy consumed by electrical components (E_{el}), (ii) the energy required for signal amplification, and (iii) how far away the final destination is from the relay node (D). The formula below can be used to determine the amount of energy needed to transport b bits of data between sensor nodes (SNs) [35].

$$E_{j, \text{Etx}} = \begin{cases} b \cdot E_{el} + b \cdot \epsilon_{fs} \cdot D^2, & \text{if } D < D_0 \\ b \cdot E_{el} + b \cdot \epsilon_{ap} \cdot D^4, & \text{if } D \geq D_0 \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

$$D_0 = \sqrt{(\epsilon_{fs} / \epsilon_{ap})} \tag{5}$$

Equation (4) defines the threshold distance, denoted as D_0 . If the distance between sensor nodes (SNs) is less than this threshold, the energy required for transmission increases proportionally to the square of the distance. On the other hand, when the distance exceeds this threshold, the energy demand rises exponentially, scaling with the fourth power of the distance. Next, we examine the energy consumption involved in receiving data.

$$E_{rx} = b * E_{el} \quad (6)$$

An important factor in receiving b bits, as shown in equation (6), is the energy consumed by electrical components. So, adding all the energy spent on sending and receiving b bits gives you the total energy needed for the process. The following is the formula for the total energy consumption ($E_{j,total}$) that results from communicating b bits, derived from equations (4) and (6)

$$E_{j,total} = \begin{cases} 2 * b * E_{el} + b * \epsilon_{fs} * D^2, & \text{if } D < D_0 \\ 2 * b * E_{el} + b * \epsilon_{ap} * D^4, & \text{if } D \geq D_0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The residual energy (E_{res}) of node j denotes the energy remaining after the transmission and reception of a packet, represented as follows:

$$E_{j,res} = E_0 - E_{j,total} \quad (8)$$

6. Proposed MEEGWO Algorithm

This section offers a comprehensive elucidation of the suggested algorithm. The clustering method comprises two essential phases: the CH selection phase and the cluster creation phase

Cluster Head Selection: The identification of Cluster Heads (CHs) within the network is executed via the Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) methodology. Cluster heads are generally chosen based on multiple criteria, including distance, residual energy, and node degree within the sensor network. The suggested protocol, MEEGWO, introduces an additional parameter known as the CH balance factor to improve the CH selection process.

At the commencement of the network operation, all sensor nodes transmit their exact locations and residual energy levels to the Base Station (BS). The BS leverages the MEEGWO-based clustering technique, utilizing a fitness function that incorporates many parameters, such as residual energy, proximity to the sink, intracluster distance, and the CH balance factor for cluster formation.

The primary aim of MEEGWO is to enhance CH selection to prolong the overall network lifespan. Four essential characteristics are utilized to do this: average intracluster distance, distance of cluster heads from the sink, average residual energy, and the cluster head balancing factor.

The following part delineates the terminologies utilized in the proposed protocol and offers a comprehensive elucidation of the fitness function applied.

Parameters for implementing the MEEGWO algorithm are as follows

1. n : Total count of active SNs.
2. m : Total count of CHs.
3. S : The collection of SNs is represented as $S = \{s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_n\}$.
4. C : The collection of CHs, represented as $C = \{CH_1, CH_2, \dots, CH_m\}$.
5. l_j : Total SNs in cluster j .
6. D_{max} : Max. Coverage of a SN.
7. R_{max} : Max. Coverage of a CH.
8. T_H : Energy threshold for CH candidacy.
9. D_0 : Threshold distance.
10. E_{sk} : primary energy of SN s_k , where $1 \leq k \leq n$.
11. E_{CHj} : present energy of CH_j , where $1 \leq j \leq m$.
12. $Comm(sk)$: All nodes within communication range of node s_k .
13. $Dis(sk, s_j)$: The distance between SN_{s_k} and SN_{s_j}
14. $Dis(sk, CH_j)$: The distance between SN_{s_k} and CH_j
15. $Dis(CH_j, BS)$: The distance between CH_j and BS .

Fitness function: The expression for Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) provided here appears to involve the product of SNs distances to their respective Cluster Heads (CHs), summed over all clusters (j), where each SNs distance to its CH is multiplied by its cluster size (l_j). This expression can be interpreted as the total distance between SNs and their corresponding CHs, weighted according to the quantity of nodes inside each cluster.

Average intra-cluster distance (F1)

$$F1 = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\frac{1}{l_j} \sum_{k=1}^{l_j} dis(sk, CH_j) \right) \quad (9)$$

The sink distance average is computed by dividing the distance among the BS and the CH by the total number of SNs within that CH. Therefore, minimizing this distance is necessary for energy conservation. The formula for this calculation of Average sink distance (F2) as follows

$$F2 = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\frac{1}{l_j} dis(CH_j, BS) \right) \quad (10)$$

Given that the network's lifespan hinges on energy utilization, minimizing energy consumption is of utmost importance. As maximizing total energy is necessary, the inverse of this parameter is considered to balance each objective function. Here residual energy (F3) is

$$F3 = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^m (E_{CHj})} \quad (11)$$

Balancing the clusters is essential. The arbitrary arrangement of SNs may lead to the formation of both big and tiny clusters. Therefore, this parameter is considered to ensure energy consumption is evenly distributed Cluster Head Balancing Factor (F4)

$$F4 = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{n}{m} - l_j \quad (12)$$

instead of minimizing each fitness function separately, it is more effective to minimize the aggregate of the fitness functions specified below, as seen in Equation (13)

$$\text{Fitness Funtion} = a \times F_1 + b \times F_2 + a \times F_3 + (1 - a + b + c) \times F_4 \quad (13)$$

Where a, b, and c are constant function $a + b + c = 1$

Figure 3 Shows Flowchart of Proposed algorithm

System Model:

The simulation setup for the proposed scheme involves a immobile node operating within a Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) with residual energy. This study focuses on clustering-based WSNs, which utilize rotation and selection of Cluster Heads (CHs). Communication in WSNs occurs in two phases: (1) cluster formation and CH identification, and (2) data exchange between child nodes and the Base Station (BS). As shown in Figure 3, the research scenario features 100 energy-efficient sensor nodes (SNs) randomly distributed across a 400x400 square meter area, with the Base Station centrally positioned within this region. The proposed MEEGWO algorithm is implemented to determine the optimal routing path between the CHs and the BS.

Simulation parameter

Total nodes deployed	200
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WSN designated area	400 *400 m ²
The Primary Energy of nodes	0.5J
Packet length	50 bits
Energy use in Transceiver Idle State	50 nJ/bit
Data Aggregation Energy	5nJ/bit/report
Amplification Energy $E_{fs}(D < D_o)$	10pJ/bit/m ²
Amplification Energy $E_{ap}(D \geq D_o)$	0.0013pJ/bit/ m ⁴

The efficacy of the suggested MEEGWO algorithm is assessed against the established MLEACH and Fuzzy algorithms utilizing MATLAB. The simulation program incorporates the following parameters for the wireless sensor network (WSN): (I) Sensor nodes are randomly dispersed within the designated region, (II) Once deployed, the positions of the sensor nodes are immutable, (III) The position of the Base Station (BS) is adjustable. (IV) At the outset, all nodes possess identical residual energy, established at 0.5J. (V) The energy harvesting rate for the nodes is determined to be 0.00010J. Supplementary simulation parameters are presented in the table.

Result Analysis:

As depicted in Figure 3, the survivability of MLEACH decreases as the number of rounds increases. MLEACH only survives for 1200 rounds. In contrast, the Fuzzy protocol manages to survive up to 1300 rounds. The figure clearly illustrates that the proposed algorithm, MEEGWO, exhibits superior performance, surviving up to 1600 rounds. Without a doubt, it can be stated that MEEGWO outperforms both of these algorithms significantly.

Figure 3. Network survivability v/s number of rounds

Figure 4. shows the progression of dead sensor nodes (SNs) as the number of iterations increases. It becomes evident that the network's longevity is influenced by the number of nodes that remain active as the rounds continue. In terms of energy efficiency, the proposed MEEGWO scheme demonstrates a network lifespan comparable to those of the MLEACH and Fuzzy cluster head selection strategies. Notably, the period between rounds 1300 and 1700 stands out, during which the proposed scheme.

Figure 4. Performance of number of dead nodes v/s number of rounds

Throughput is a crucial indicator for evaluating network reliability, reflecting the total packets received by the base station (BS) as the number of rounds escalates.. Figure 5 clearly demonstrates the superior performance of MEEGWO over the MLEACH and FUZZY strategies.

The average quantity of packets received by the base station in the MEEGWO, MLEACH, and FUZZY cluster head selection methodologies are 8.1579×10^3 , 4.6815×10^3 , and 5.8621×10^3 , respectively.

Additionally, the average network throughput of MEEGWO surpasses that of the MLEACH and FUZZY strategies by 25% and 27.5%, respectively.

Figure 5 and 6 shows the experimental results comparing our algorithm with existing ones like MLEACH and Fuzzy, conducted across various test cases with different numbers of sensors and cluster heads (CHs). Our findings demonstrate superior performance in energy consumption, network lifespan, and packet reception at the CH and packet reception at the BS.

Figure 5. Performance analysis of number packet sends to BS v/s number of rounds

Figure 6. Performance analysis of number packet sends to CH v/s number of rounds

Conclusion

This paper presents a new cluster head selection algorithm based on MEEGWO, utilizing an optimized representation of search agents and an innovative objective function. Our focus on energy efficiency incorporates factors intra-cluster distance, base station (BS) distance, and sensor residual energy. Additionally, we have devised a weighted function to promote effective cluster formation. We present experimental results comparing our algorithm with existing ones like MLEACH and Fuzzy, conducted across various test cases with different numbers of sensors and cluster heads (CHs). Our findings demonstrate superior performance in energy consumption, network lifespan, and packet reception at the BS. Furthermore, we suggest potential extensions of this work, including the development of novel routing algorithms and addressing issues like weight balancing and error tolerance in WSNs. Our experimentation has been limited to homogeneous networks, but future investigations could explore heterogeneous network environments

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